

OPTIMIZATION OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN THE STUDY OF GENERAL SURGERY IN MODERN CONDITIONS

Israilov Ibrohim Khujaerovich

Abu Ali Ibn Sina Suzangaron College of Public Health, Senior lecturer of the discipline "Fundamentals of surgery and intensive care"

Isakov Abdurauf Mamadiyarovich

Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of the Department of Anesthesiology and Intensive Care of Pediatric Surgery, Faculty of Postgraduate Education, Samarkand State Medical University

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Abstract: This article highlights the features of training students at a medical college. The main task of the clinical department, in particular the department of surgery, is to develop in students clinical thinking, a sufficient amount of theoretical knowledge and practical skills, competencies necessary for a modern doctor.

Key words: medicine, training, skills, practice, surgery.

Modern rational approaches to teaching surgery in a medical college are based on the integration of educational, medical and scientific processes; the unity and organicity of theory with practice provide for individualization and practical orientation of training, some flexibility and freedom of learning, which will help bring educational activities closer to professional ones, taking into account the needs of healthcare and new advances in surgery. With the introduction of new operations and a huge arsenal of medications, a teacher of surgery in a medical college must constantly monitor the changing standards of treatment for a particular surgical disease, be a practicing surgeon or have sufficient experience in surgery, attend surgical congresses and participate in surgical conferences.

The effectiveness of students' scientific and cognitive activities can be monitored through oral questioning, written control, laboratory and practical methods and self-control methods. The use of test tasks and tasks allows you to improve learning results. The clinic uses many ways to involve students in relevant practical activities, which develop their ability to solve problems, forming a holistic approach to patient care and performing a number of manipulations.

The constant reform of healthcare in Uzbekistan, the development of medical science, the structural and functional reorganization of medical care, the introduction of innovative promising technologies and methods of diagnosis, treatment, prevention and rehabilitation require in modern conditions to increase, improve and expand the professional level of each medical worker. The quality of medical care at various levels and the results of the work of both a specific medical institution and the entire health care system as a whole depend on this.

Improving the quality of specialist training in order to ensure his competitiveness in the labor market is one of the constants, most important tasks of higher education. 3rd year medical students are just beginning to study clinical disciplines. Their acquaintance with the clinic of surgical diseases begins with general surgery. The theoretical knowledge, skills and practical skills they acquired will serve as the basis for further study of such disciplines as faculty and hospital surgery.

Everyone knows that a shaky foundation precludes the possibility of creating a strong superstructure. It is this circumstance that explains the importance for a student of the

fundamental study of general surgery. Students, unfortunately, often have little motivation for the learning process. This circumstance requires the teacher to act effectively as an organizer and, to a certain extent, a catalyst for the educational process.

Considering the increasing competition between various educational and medical institutions, it is necessary to constantly modernize the educational process. The effectiveness of the educational process is achieved in conditions of increased activity of students by the direction of the process of organizing their learning. Today, more and more teachers believe that teaching surgical disciplines has its own characteristics. Both healthcare reform and modern development of medicine are changing the understanding of such basic principles of surgery as asepsis, antiseptics, transfusiology, surgical infection, wound treatment, local and general anesthesia, surgery of the acute abdomen, etc. Particular importance is attached to the promotion of medical and hygienic knowledge, disease prevention, and education of a healthy lifestyle. The development of modern world technologies, the use of modern computer technology requires more intense and responsible work in the training of medical personnel in educational institutions.

Modern rational approaches to teaching surgery in a medical college are based on the integration of educational, medical and scientific processes; the unity and organicity of theory with practice provide for individualization and practical orientation of training, some flexibility and freedom of learning, which will help bring educational activities closer to professional ones, taking into account the needs of healthcare and new advances in surgery. The educational process in a medical college is based on andragogical principles, such as joint activities of the student with the teacher in organizing the learning process, starting with the formulation of educational goals and drawing up a training plan, personal initiative and activity in acquiring knowledge, skills, awareness of learning, the ability to work in team, updating learning results, motivation for learning, which is decisive for the degree of its effectiveness.

The basic element of the educational process, the basis for all new organizational forms of training, remains verbal teaching methods, namely lecture, conversation, report, instruction, round table. The development of technology has opened up new opportunities that make it possible to use visuals in teaching at all levels. Illustration, observation, demonstration contribute to better understanding of a specific topic by students. The use of innovative technologies, active and interactive teaching methods is necessary and justified. During training, manuals, methodological recommendations, special medical literature, video materials, Internet publications, electronic libraries, materials of conferences, congresses and congresses of surgeons are widely used.

Practical classes in surgical disciplines have their own characteristics. Both in preclinical practice rooms and on the basis of surgical, traumatological, gynecological and other surgical departments, students of the medical college are engaged in practicing surgical skills and tasks. Thanks to this, students acquire the necessary knowledge and skills, which contributes to the organic combination of theory and practice.

To achieve high quality learning, various methods are used depending on the type of cognitive activity to stimulate interest in learning. To develop a student's attention, the information-receptive method is used, to consolidate knowledge, develop skills and abilities - the reproductive method, and to develop logic - the problem method. Thanks to disputes,

discussions, independent work with literature, and the Internet, students' interest in learning is stimulated.

The effectiveness of students' scientific and cognitive activities can be monitored through oral questioning, written control, laboratory and practical methods and self-control methods. The use of test tasks and tasks allows you to improve learning results. Test tasks are developed by topic, as well as in aggregate for the final lesson.

The tasks of a surgery teacher at a medical college are not only to consolidate students acquired theoretical and practical skills, but also to develop in future specialists a sense of responsibility towards work and patients, a sense of compassion and dedication. With the introduction of new operations and a huge arsenal of medications, a teacher of surgery in a medical college must constantly monitor the changing standards of treatment for a particular surgical disease, be a practicing surgeon or have sufficient experience in surgery, attend surgical congresses and participate in surgical conferences.

Thus, the existing system of training medical college students in surgical disciplines provides all the necessary opportunities for the continuous development of professionally qualified specialists, allows us to train not only competitive, highly qualified professionals, but also creative individuals with high spiritual and ethical principles.

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